

Bias in Human Origins Research

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Abstract

How we approach and study human evolution has significant implications for our understanding of the processes that define and differentiate *Homo sapiens* from other hominins. As such, it is imperative that human origins research strives to reflect the broad spectrum of humanity's diversity and its varied perspectives as much as possible. While European colonialism and its legacy have substantially shaped the study of human evolution and its sources of knowledge, the extent and impact of their influence have not yet been quantified. Here we demonstrate a range of systemic geographic biases in human origins research that are the outcome of long-term colonial and neo-imperial influence on research agendas and practices. We find that the discipline is dominated by a narrow cohort of researchers, institutions, and funding bodies from a small number of Global North countries. Furthermore, we find that these institutions exercise undue influence on human origins research in the Global South, with representation from Global South researchers and institutions remaining critically low up to the present day. We observe that the European archaeological and fossil record remains an area of intensive and on-going research focus, while the vast continents of Africa, Asia, and Australia remain acutely under-researched. We recommend a reorientation of the discipline to meaningfully engage with Indigenous and Global South communities and researchers, and their perspectives on the human story, and call for a shift of attention to under-represented areas of the Eastern Hemisphere, allowing for a more informed and inclusive picture of the ways in which humans evolved.

Main

Human origins research had its inception during the era of European empire building, with significant implications for our understanding of our species' evolution and history. Colonial biases shaped research questions, interpretations, and practices in fundamental ways¹, and these biases persist through to the present day. Scholars have highlighted, for example, the damaging effects that evolutionary theories had on Indigenous peoples during the colonial period, arguing that negative discourses about particular groups remain embedded in present-day research agendas¹⁻³. Furthermore, various forms of bias established in the colonial period, with regards to the power and reach of particular institutions, the locations of field research, and the constitution of the academy remain endemic within the natural sciences⁴⁻⁶ and in human origins research^{1,7-10}, influencing evolutionary concepts and research practices¹¹⁻¹³. As such, argue that contemporary human origins research is the product of a disciplinary legacy that has shaped a biased and incomplete account of human biocultural diversity and evolution^{14,15}.

One primary axis of enduring human origins research bias relates to research in and by the Global North versus the Global South. While definitions vary, the Global South is broadly construed as countries that have been on the receiving end of imperialism and colonial rule¹⁶, while countries belonging to the Global North have benefited from the resulting inequitable flow of wealth and capital¹⁷. Following the United Nations and the World Bank, we include North America, Europe, and Australia as part of the Global North, and Africa, Asia (excluding Israel, Japan, and South Korea), and Latin America as geopolitically part of the Global South¹⁸. While modern research institutions in the Global North increasingly prioritise diversity in the academy¹⁹⁻²², they nevertheless operate within an

inherited institutional framework in which systemic bias strongly circumscribes the inclusion of a diversity of perspectives^{14,15,23-28}. Socio-economic inequality between the Global North and Global South impacts representation in human origins research, with unequal opportunities for education, training, fieldwork and publication, as well as the flow of information and data, overwhelmingly benefiting Global North researchers and institutions, and shaping research discourse and findings^{10,29-32}.

Here we bring together a diverse group of Global North, Global South, and Indigenous researchers to examine the role of colonial and neo-imperial derived bias on research into human origins, drawing on working group consultations developed as part of the Human Origins and Our Future Workshop, held in Brisbane in January 2024. We define human origins research as the study of *Homo sapiens* and our hominin relatives, investigated primarily through human palaeontology, genetics, and archaeology. In light of our authorship, our study focuses on research on landmasses in the Eastern Hemisphere (Africa, Asia, Europe, Australia) that were occupied prior to the Holocene. We systematically examine four potential forms of bias in the field of human origins research. Firstly, we investigate bias in researcher affiliations using published data from the extensive and scientifically influential *Scopus* database, emphasising disparities and trends in the global production of research outputs. Secondly, we examine *Scopus* data to ascertain where the institutions and funding bodies undertaking human origins research are located, and where research funding is being allocated. Thirdly, we examine the large-scale *Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans* (ROCEEH) *Out of Africa Database* (ROAD) to explore sampling bias in human origins research. Finally, we examine affiliation data in the *Scopus* dataset to investigate decadal patterns in two case studies (Tanzania, Australia) to assess trends in Global South and Indigenous involvement in human origins research. It should be noted that while the *Scopus* and ROAD databases contain valuable information on patterns of global research, they do not offer a complete picture of human origins research, which is also frequently published in non-indexed regional journals and in a variety of languages not captured in the global archives.

Who is leading human origins research?

The question of who dominates research programs in human origins is critical to understanding how disciplinary research topics and themes are prioritised and investigated³³. If researchers derive from a narrow cohort, then there is a risk that a commensurate, and potentially limited, range of questions and priorities will influence the discipline^{10,12,14,34}.

To investigate the degree of potential bias within human origins research, author affiliation data listed on publications focusing on research conducted in and on Africa, Asia, Europe, and Australia were extracted using multiple queries submitted to the *Scopus* database³⁵ (see Methods). An important academic bias immediately apparent in these results is the overrepresentation of English language journals in *Scopus*. Indeed, one recent analysis found that while the *Scopus* database contained documents in over 50 languages, 93% of those indexed were in English, with the most represented non-English languages being Chinese, French, German, and Spanish³⁶ (the latter three reflecting ongoing Eurocentric bias). While language bias in the *Scopus* database is apparent, it is nevertheless the largest compendium of peer-reviewed literature in the world, and it remains useful for investigating global scientific influence and impact.

When comparing the percentage of affiliations deriving from individual countries, we find distinct geographic and cultural biases within the cohort of human origins researchers reflected in *Scopus*. Human origins researchers deriving from just a handful of Global North countries dominate publications across all four regions investigated, with only South African and Chinese researchers

representing the Global South in the top ten nations contributing to published research for each region (Table 1). Institutions based in the United States of America (USA) and the United Kingdom (UK) form a dominant global cohort in the publication sample (Table 1). Together the USA and UK comprise 39-43% of researcher affiliations for human origins research focused on Africa, Asia, and Europe, demonstrating the extraordinary influence and global reach of academics based in these two countries alone. Only one African country, South Africa, makes the list for research into human origins on the African continent, contributing ~16% of research affiliations (Table 1). Russia and China both make the top five countries for the Asian continental region, although their contributions are dwarfed by those of the USA and UK (Table 1). Australia is the only example where home country institutions take a dominant lead in research affiliations for their region, contributing 78% of affiliations. While the UK occupies the top position for Europe, it is closely followed by the USA.

Table 1 Affiliations by country (top 10) for publications on human origins research focused on Africa, Asia, Europe, and Australia³⁵.

	Africa	%	Asia	%	Europe	%	Australia	%
1	US	27.0	US	22.4	UK	24.3	Australia	77.7
2	South Africa	16.1	UK	16.5	US	18.7	US	6.3
3	UK	13.8	Russia	12.1	France	9.2	UK	6.2
4	France	13.7	Australia	11.7	Spain	7.2	New Zealand	2.8
5	Germany	6.8	China	10.1	Russia	6.6	France	2.6
6	Australia	5.5	France	6.6	Germany	6.0	Germany	0.9
7	Spain	3.8	Germany	5.3	Netherlands	4.1	Canada	0.6
8	China	1.4	Spain	2.2	Australia	3.3	Spain	0.6
9	Norway	1.4	Israel	1.3	Italy	3.1	Netherlands	0.5
10	Portugal	1.2	Japan	1.1	Poland	2.7	South Africa	0.4
Top 5		77.4		72.8		65.9		95.5
Top 10		90.7		89.3		85.1		98.5

When we compare research affiliations by larger geographic regions, researcher-origin bias becomes even more evident (Figure 1A-B). Researchers focusing on human origins in African nations predominantly originate from institutions within Europe (44%) and North America (27%) (Supplementary Information 1 Table S5, Table S9). Only 20% of affiliations on Africa-centred research articles derive from institutions within the African continent. For research on human origins in Asia, similar patterns can be observed, with 16% of researcher affiliations linked to Asian nations, and approximately two thirds of these being Chinese institutions. European and North American affiliations dominate (36% and 23%) (Supplementary Information 1 Table S6, Table S10). Conversely, the sample of publications on human origins studies centred on Europe shows that research is overwhelmingly undertaken by European affiliated researchers (presumably largely European nationals) (Figure 1B). Affiliations from African and Asian institutions on publications about Europe total only 0.4% and 3.6% respectively, demonstrating an even greater disparity in researcher affiliations from African and Asian institutions operating outside of their own geographic regions (Supplementary Information 1 Table S7, Table S11). We also note that Global North countries located in the Asian geographic region (Israel, Japan, and South Korea) comprise ~50% of Asian affiliations for publications on human origins in Africa, Europe, and Australia. The only geographic region where Asian Global South researcher affiliations dominate is for publications on human origins in Asia itself, led by China. Australia is unusual when compared to the other continental regions examined; Australian researchers comprise 78% of the total affiliations for Australia-focused human origins

research, demonstrating an even greater local focus than seen in Europe (Supplementary Information 1 Table S8, Table S12). However, less than 4% of Australians today are Indigenous, and the country's current population broadly reflects recent European colonisation³⁷.

Figure 1 Systemic biases in human origins research across four key global regions. **A** Continental regions examined in B and C, with total land area shown for each (topographic data obtained from the GEBCO 2014 Grid, version 20150318, <http://www.gebco.net>). **B** Researcher affiliations by geographic region for publications on human origins research centred on Africa, Asia, Europe and Australia compiled from Scopus data³⁵. **C** Funding sponsors by geographic region for publications on human origins research centred on Africa, Asia, Europe and Australia compiled from Scopus data³⁵. Russia forms its own category as it falls into both Europe and Asia.

Who is funding human origins research?

Funding bodies, institutions, and organisations listed on human origins publications within our dataset for Africa, Asia, Europe, and Australia follow similar patterns to those described above. To investigate the degree of potential bias, information was extracted from the *Scopus* database³⁵ following the methods detailed for the affiliation data (Methods, Supplementary Information 1 Table S13-S16). Individual funding bodies based in the USA lead on research publications for Africa (28%), with the National Science Foundation listed on 8% of papers, followed by the Leakey Foundation (4%) (Supplementary Information 1 Table S13). South African sponsors comprise 11%, led by the National Research Foundation (4%). Individual funding bodies appearing on Asia-centred human origins publications were more diverse, led by the National Science Foundation (USA, 7%), the National Natural Science Foundation of China (5%), and the Australian Research Council (5%) (Supplementary Information 1 Table S14). In contrast, European funding bodies dominate research on Europe, led by EU-affiliated institutions and programs (e.g., European Commission, European Research Council) (Supplementary Information 1 Table S15). The Australian Research Council is overwhelmingly dominant as a funding sponsor listed on publications for Australia (34%) (Supplementary Information 1 Table S16).

When funding bodies based in the four continental regions are aggregated, European sponsors lead for research focused on Africa, Asia, and Europe (43%, 34%, and 69%, respectively), followed closely by North American sponsors for publications on Asia (33%), with a more significant US funding lag for publications on Africa and Europe (30%, and 16%) (Supplementary Information 1 Tables S22-S24). Australian funding bodies dominate human origins research in Australia, contributing 76% of acknowledged funding on publications in our sample (Supplementary Information 1 Table S25). In contrast, Australian funding bodies comprise only 4%, 8%, and 3% of funders acknowledged on publications for Africa, Asia, and Europe. Funding sponsors from African and Asian nations were declared on 14% and 21% of human origins publications relating to their own respective regions, with the majority of these being South African and Chinese. Again, African funding bodies had little reach beyond their geographic region, with no African funders listed on human origins publications for Europe or Australia in our sample. Asian funding sponsors were listed on 6%, 4%, and 1% of human origins publications for Africa, Europe, and Australia, respectively, achieving a similar reach to Australian financial bodies.

What is driving sampling bias in human origins research?

Biases in the leadership and funding of human origins research inevitably shape choices concerning its geographic focus, including both the location and intensity of research efforts. An overfocus on some regions at the expense of others potentially has considerable implications for our understanding of human evolution and human diversity. To investigate the degree of sampling bias in human origins research, we examined published data ROAD^{38,39} (Methods, Supplementary Information 1 Table S26, Supplementary Information 2). ROAD reflects a trend in recent decades to aggregate existing information on human origins into big data collections contained in open access online databases^{38,40,41}. These databases provide an invaluable tool for both safeguarding knowledge, and allowing for large-scale data interrogation of spatial, temporal, and cultural trends. ROCEEH is a 20-year (2008-2027) research centre based in Germany, with an impressive mission to understand the process of ‘becoming human’, covering the evolution of *Homo* and the story of expansion from Africa through multiple migration waves. ROAD contains data from Africa and Eurasia spanning 3,000,000 to 20,000 years ago and represents the largest aggregation of information on human origins currently available for analysis.

While ROAD represents a laudable and important initiative, it also, like all such projects, reflects sampling bias⁴², multiple forms of which are acknowledged by the project team. The database includes a selected number of ‘well-published’ sites judged to be of ‘high quality’ from a sample of time periods for each country covered by the database. As of early 2023, the database contained information pertaining to >1700 unique sites from more than 5,000 published articles³⁸. Articles published in English and continental European languages (French, German, Spanish, Italian, and Russian) dominate, with increased inclusion of Chinese language articles following the addition of two native speakers to the team³⁸. The project acknowledges that a large proportion of the publications included in ROAD derive from only a handful of English language journals, with the team emphasising the need for a greater inclusion of non-Western sources³⁸.

Figure 2 **A** Percentage of human origins sites for Africa, Asia, Europe, and Sahul (Australia and New Guinea) aggregated from the ROAD (CC BY-SA 4.0 ROCEEH Out of Africa Database) and SahulArch, compared against the percentage of total land area for all four regions. **B** Distribution of human origins sites contained in the

ROAD database at time of publication (orange points), and **B1** SahulArch database (blue points). **C** Heat map of the density of human origin sites contained in ROAD and **C1** aggregated data from ROAD and the SahulArch database.

A source of unacknowledged bias in ROAD resides in the choice of countries and regions selected for inclusion in the database. Of importance is the unexplained decision by the ROAD project to exclude Sahul (the Pleistocene continental landmass encompassing Australia and New Guinea at times of lower sea level) from its database, despite the project's focus on human expansions and despite the presence in Sahul of *Homo sapiens* archaeological sites older than those known from western Europe. Therefore, in order to enable assessment of potential geographic and sampling bias in Sahul, as well as to demonstrate a key omission of ROAD, we examined site data from the *SahulArch* repository available from the *Open Geospatial Consortium* OCTOPUS database^{40,41,43,44} (see Methods). As Sahul persisted as a continental landmass until ~8,000 years ago (when sea level rose rapidly following the end of the last glacial⁴⁵), data for Australia and New Guinea were aggregated. We plotted archaeological and fossil site distributions and densities for both ROAD and SahulArch, and highlighted regions of intensive research focus, as well as the vast geographic gaps in current research on human evolution (Figure 2).

While the ROAD data suffers from various internal sampling biases, it is nevertheless a useful tool for examining bias in human origins research. This is revealed for example by the distribution of fossil and archaeological sites across Africa, Asia, and Europe in the ROAD dataset, which reflects both sampling and research bias with finds published in regional languages broadly excluded, often in the same regions where less research has taken place. At the time of writing (and with the project nearing completion), ROAD demonstrated a considerable disparity in the number of European sites compared to African and Asian sites relating to human origins research (Figure 2A). When we consider the vast difference in the size of these landmasses, which combined cover ~85 million km², the underlying sampling bias is clear. While Europe accounts for 46% of all human origins sites in the database at the time of writing, it covers only 12% of total land area (~10 million km²; Figures 1A, 2A), excluding Australia. In contrast, the African continent has a landmass three times larger than Europe (36% of the total land area, excluding Australia, ~30 million km²), but currently accounts for only ~26% of sites contained in ROAD. These sites are also tellingly distributed along the eastern and southern edge of Africa, primarily in nations that experienced prolonged European colonisation. The disparity in coverage is even greater for the largest continental region included in the database. While Asia accounts for 52% of total landmass, excluding Australia, (~44 million km²), it currently contains only ~28% of total human origins sites recorded within the ROAD database.

The ROAD data reveals an even stronger sampling bias when total site numbers per country are considered. In fact, 82% of the countries included in ROAD at the time of writing individually contribute less than 1% of the total dataset (Supplementary Information 1 Table S26, Supplementary Information 2). France leads, by a large majority, with >14% of all sites. Together with Italy and Germany, it forms the densest cluster of sites seen in Europe in Figure 2C, which also represents the highest density cluster across the three continents. It is of note that outside of these three European countries, most nations in Europe individually contribute less than 1% of total sites, demonstrating regional bias within Europe itself. Of the 33 African countries contained in ROAD at the time of writing, South Africa dominates site counts (8% of total sites in ROAD) for the African continent (~26% of total sites) and contains the highest global proportion of known sites in the database outside of France. The second highest density cluster of sites per region in Africa is situated in Kenya, Tanzania, and Ethiopia, which individually contribute between ~2-4% of total sites, with Morocco and

Egypt at 1.3% and 1.1%, respectively. The majority of the remaining 27 countries included each contribute between 0.1-0.2% to the database. Individual Asian nations show similar patterns, with China and Indonesia each contributing ~5% of total sites within the database, the highest percentage of any individual country within the Asian region. Chinese human origins sites are relatively evenly distributed, while most Indonesian sites are concentrated on a single island (Java, Figure 2C). At present, vast regions of western and northern Africa remain effectively unknown to human evolutionary studies, with many individual African nations in these regions contributing no site information at all in the ROAD database. Similarly, most countries within Asia currently contribute less than 1% of sites, with much of the story of human origins across the vast Asian continental region either absent from the database or remaining unknown to western science (Figure 2B-C).

When the ROAD and *SahulArch* data are combined, Australia and New Guinea (continental Sahul until ~8,000 years ago) are found to contribute 9% of total human origin sites for all four continental regions. The two islands have a combined land area equating to 9% of total land area for the four continental regions (~8.5 million km²), and Australia as a continent is the smallest region with the lowest site count (Figure 2A). When considered individually as a country, Australia (southern Sahul) contributes 8% of known sites, second only to France and leading South Africa in the aggregated dataset. The highest density of known sites is concentrated in the southeast corner of the continent where contemporary populations are highest, and in a hot spot region in the northwest, where concentrated mining activities have occurred for decades driving sustained heritage investigations (Figure 2 B1-C1). Vast areas of the arid interior and the northeast of the continent are devoid of known sites. Mining and urban development activities appear to be driving the discovery of sites and, with this, research foci across Australia, in addition to geographic selection bias on the part of archaeologists⁴⁶. New Guinea (northern Sahul) has extremely low site counts (<1% of sites in the aggregated dataset), which are concentrated in a few areas in the eastern half of the island.

State of the discipline

Our study has identified multiple forms of systemic bias in human origins databases and studies, with research chiefly undertaken and funded by Global North nations, perpetuating historical colonial authority over the human origins narrative. This impact is strongly demonstrated by the pre-eminence of European and North American institutions working in the African and Asian continental regions, with those from the USA and UK overwhelmingly dominating global research output for these regions. Representation from researchers with affiliations to Global South institutions is generally extremely low, particularly outside of their geographic regions.

Despite growing recognition that human origins research needs to move beyond its myopic focus on Europe, western Europe remains a dominant research focus within the discipline. Accordingly, Eurocentric models of human evolution continue to play a key role in human origins research^{8,12,47}, creating geographic biases in exploration and research and exacerbating institutional inequities. It is clear from our investigation of the *Scopus* and ROAD data that European human origins questions, specifically those relating to France, Germany, and Italy, have received disproportionate research effort and investment. Such an intensive focus on a comparatively small region is in stark contrast to the bounded and/or extremely limited information available for the vast and critical landmasses of Africa and Asia.

The regions of Africa, Asia, and Sahul that show substantial gaps or demonstrate low site counts highlight multiple forms of potential bias. Though site preservation issues must always be considered⁴⁶, these regions almost certainly contain rich human origins records that are absent for several other possible reasons, none of them mutually exclusive. Firstly, a recent study investigating

bias in the editorial process found manuscripts from Asian countries were five times more likely to be rejected⁴⁸, highlighting systemic geographic bias in publication success. Secondly, data for these regions may be published within regional journals that are not online or indexed and in languages that are not included in the global databases^{34,36,38}. Thirdly, and most importantly, the regional gaps may also reflect real geographic biases and point to regions where interdisciplinary work on human evolution has not been funded.

We highlight the exclusion of Sahul from the ROAD database. Representing the *terminus ante quem* for the Out of Africa dispersals, Sahul belongs in datasets that explore questions about our species' origins and early dispersals. With *Homo sapiens* reaching the island continent by ~65,000 years ago⁴⁹⁻⁵², well before their first appearance in Europe^{53,54}, and with dispersal across the continent by ~50,000 years ago⁵⁵⁻⁶², the exclusion of the heritage of Australian Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people from a major human origins and expansions database is a critical omission.

Emerging trends

Global North countries and academics dominate human origins research, and although important steps are being taken to address such biases across science⁶³⁻⁶⁶, we do not see evidence of any radical change in this trend in human origins research. We examined the percentage of affiliations representing Indigenous and Global South researchers listed on a sample of human origins publications in *Scopus*³⁵. We included publications from the past 55 years (1970 to present), and specifically examined two regions as case studies, Tanzania, and Australia. We chose Tanzania as the 'ground zero' of human origins research in Africa, with many extraordinary fossil finds originating from Olduvai Gorge, the location from which human origins scientific narratives have often stemmed since the 1950s⁶⁷⁻⁷⁰. Additionally, this country represents a former colony of Germany and the UK that achieved self-governance in 1961. Australia was chosen as a case study as it forms the terminal end of the first great dispersal arc from Africa⁷¹⁻⁷⁵. Colonised by the UK in 1788, the country comprises a majority Global North population encapsulating a minority Indigenous population.

In the first decade (1970-1979), international (i.e., non-African nations) research affiliations were exclusively listed on Tanzanian human origins publications in our sample (Figure 2A) (Supplementary Information 1 Table S28, Supplementary Information 3). The 1980s saw somewhat increased regional representation, with Tanzanian affiliations comprising 10% of listed institutions. However, after the 1980s, Tanzanian representation plummeted, only beginning to gradually increase again in the 2000s. The past half decade has seen the upward trend continuing, with Tanzanian institutions comprising 12% of researcher affiliations in 2020-2024, following the US and Spain (36% and 17%).

Within Australia, local affiliations declined steadily through the first four decades (1970-2009), dropping from 75% to 32% over this period (Supplementary Information 1 Table S29, Supplementary Information 3). By the decade 2000-2009, international institutions (non-Australian) had increased to 68% of those listed on publications for human origins on the continent (Figure 3B). Moreover, between 1970 and 1999, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Australian affiliations are non-existent in our sample. The reasons for this result are likely complex; on the one hand archaeologists sought to conduct joint research with Aboriginal communities, and on the other, Indigenous peoples refused to participate in research that was considered to be historically colonial and racist, with little positive value for their lives and cultures⁷⁶. Following the pattern seen in Tanzania, an important shift occurred within the decade 2000-2009, with the first inclusion of affiliations linked to Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Australian organisations and communities. From 2020-2024, affiliations representing Indigenous Australians comprise 25% of Australian institutions on human origins publications pertaining to Australia. Overall, our results demonstrate an upward trend in local

Tanzanian researcher and Australian Indigenous involvement in publications through time, particularly for Australia, and most significantly in the past half-decade (Figure 3), including co-design of projects by Indigenous corporations and non-Indigenous authors. However, only four Indigenous Australians have so far graduated from a PhD program in archaeology⁷⁷, and as a result, Indigenous academic leadership, while impactful, remains low. Nevertheless, the publication trend offers encouraging signs that Indigenous and Global South representation within the discipline is growing, at least in these two countries. The degree to which Indigenous and Global South knowledges and perspectives drive joint research, however, remains somewhat unclear. However, in the case of Australia, clear government mandates for increased Indigenous control of archaeological heritage⁷⁸ have undoubtedly played a key role in shifting landscapes of inclusivity.

Figure 3 **A** Percentage of international, Tanzanian, and other African Nation affiliations on publications on human origins in Tanzania by decade, compiled from the Scopus database. **B** Percentage of international, Australian, and Aboriginal Australian affiliations on publications on Australia by decade, compiled from the Scopus database.

Conclusion

What knowledge are we missing as a result of the pervasive existence of bias in human origins research? Our findings would seem to suggest that our epistemological lacunae are potentially substantial, with profound implications for our datasets, models, and overall understanding of human origins. Furthermore, despite the increase in representation of Indigenous and Global South researchers and collaborators in our two case studies, the degree to which they currently drive research agenda and shape research questions in the field of human evolution remains unclear. Having identified institutional and geographic bias, we argue that it is an ethical imperative that more diverse perspectives are included in research into human origins, with particular attention needed to ensure fuller Indigenous and Global South researcher participation. To this end, we argue that community partnerships are fundamental to the progress of scientific research⁷⁹ and that integration of traditional, Indigenous, and other minority knowledge into the scientific process will pay dividends for transdisciplinary human origins research, as has been shown in numerous cases⁸⁰⁻⁸⁵. Furthermore, such efforts will also yield greater benefits for communities themselves^{83,86,87}. Research clearly shows that making space for fresh and diverse perspectives increases innovation⁸⁸⁻⁹¹, and within human origins research a more inclusive approach has the potential not only to move the discipline forward in critical ways, but also to breathe new life into biased and sometimes stale debates, ultimately generating wholly new areas of deliberation⁹². Most importantly, the inclusion of

Indigenous perspectives and collaborative community partnerships is essential to efforts to address past epistemic injustices and ongoing challenges of epistemological inequality surrounding human origins research^{93,94}. The ongoing debate and shifting perspectives surrounding the respectful treatment of ancestral remains and their culturally appropriate repatriation^{95,96} as well as the representation of cultural remains in Global North museums⁹⁷ points toward growing acknowledgement of the importance of including Indigenous and Global South perspectives in the development of human origins research as a reflective and responsible academic endeavour.

Redressing the imbalance in the geographic foci and institutional and funding biases identified here is likely to be a lengthy process that will span generations. It will involve deliberate shifts in research focus, active recruitment of Global South and Indigenous researchers^{23,98}, and targeted funding of Global South research initiatives and institutions and Indigenous representation bodies to support training and development of future, more diverse generations of academics in human origins research. In this way, the broader global research community can begin to reshape the human story to include more of the world's rich histories and perspectives, and in so doing, increase the value, inclusivity, and relevance of human origins research for a far greater proportion of humanity.

Methods

Affiliation and funding data

We investigated bias in researcher affiliations and funding institutions using published data from the Scopus³⁵ database (<https://www.scopus.com>), focusing on publications on human origins research conducted in and on Africa, Asia, Europe and Australia. Data was obtained by submitting multiple queries to the Scopus database³⁵. Queries were constrained by a defined range of search terms and their variants and combinations (hominin, *Homo*, *Homo sapiens*, archaic human, modern human, evolution, dispersal, fossil, archaeology) (Supplementary Information 1), and repeated for each continental region (i.e., Africa, Asia, Europe, Australia). Query results were refined through the *Key Word* and *Source Title* tools, with ~60 additional key words suggested by Scopus for each geographic region. Scopus *Subject Areas* were restricted to the Social Sciences, Earth and Planetary Sciences, Arts and Humanities, Multidisciplinary, and Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology categories. The 'Documents by affiliation' and 'Documents by funding sponsor' datasets were accessed through the Scopus *Analyze results* tool. Queries retrieved a sample of between ~1700-3000 affiliations (Supplementary Information 1 Tables S1-S4) and between ~600-1100 funding institutions (Supplementary Information 1 Tables S13-S16) sourced from ~400-500 publications for each continent. Home country was assigned to each affiliation and funding institution, and countries ranked by total number of affiliations and funding institutions (Supplementary Information 1 Tables S5-S8 and Tables S17-S20). Affiliation and funding institution data for individual countries was collated into African Nations, Asian Nations, Australia, European Nations, Russia, and South American Nations (Supplementary Information 1 Tables S9-S12 and S22-S25). Australia was treated as a distinct continental region, and Russia formed its own category as it encompasses both the Asian and European geographic regions. As affiliations from institutions in Asia fall into both Global North and Global South countries, percentages were given for each group.

Sampling bias data

To investigate sampling bias in human origins research, we examined published data contained in the Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans (ROCEEH) (<https://www.hadw-bw.de/en/research/research-center/roceeh>) Out of Africa Database (ROAD)^{38,39} (https://www.roceeh.uni-tuebingen.de/roadweb/smarty_road_simple_search.php). Spatial

coordinates for all sites contained in ROAD (spanning 3,000,000 to 20,000 years ago) were downloaded (database accessed on 05/03/2024; Supplementary Information 2) and projected in ESRI ArcGIS Pro. Percentage of total sites per country and geographic region (Africa, Asia, Europe, Russia) was calculated (Supplementary Information 1 Table S26). Sites located in Russia with spatial coordinates that fell within Europe or Asia were divided into the final counts for the two continental regions. To visualise heat maps showing spatial site distributions across Africa, Asia, and Europe a kernel density analysis was performed in ArcGIS Pro using point data generated from the spatial coordinates supplied in ROAD.

As ROAD does not contain site data for Sahul, this was obtained from the SahulArch repository available from the Open Geospatial Consortium OCTOPUS database (v.2) (<https://octopusdata.org/>)^{40,41,43,44}. SahulArch contains data on 2,318 archaeological sites from across Sahul. Shapefiles for sites related to human occupation were downloaded from the OSL and Radiocarbon collections. To align with ROAD, we included only archaeological site counts spanning first occupation of Sahul to 20,000 years ago (>180 sites; Supplementary Information 1 Table S27). Shapefiles were projected in ArcGIS Pro and a kernel density analysis performed to visualise density of spatial site distributions across the continent.

Case Studies – Tanzania and Australia

We examined affiliation data listed on a sample of human origins publications in Scopus³⁵ (Supplementary Information 3) focusing on two case study regions, Tanzania and Australia. Data was obtained using the methods detailed in the *Affiliation and funding data* section. We included publications from the past 55 years (1970 to present), and assessed decadal trends in representation of international, Indigenous and Global South researchers (Supplementary Information 1 Table S28-S29).

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Data Availability Statement

Researcher affiliation and funding institution data is available in the Supplementary Information, and from the Scopus database (<https://www.scopus.com>).

Spatial data is provided in the Supplementary Information, and is available on request from the creators of the Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans (ROCEEH) (<https://www.hadw-bw.de/en/research/research-center/roceeh>) Out of Africa Database (ROAD), and from the Open Geospatial Consortium OCTOPUS database (v.2) (<https://octopusdata.org/>).

Author Contributions

Conceptualisation: K.N., M.D.P., C.C., N.B. Data investigation: K.N. Graphics: K.N. Writing: K.N., N.B., M.D.P., C.S., M.P., K.P. All other authors contributed to the final manuscript: F.A., A.A., L.A., M.A., B.B., A.M.B., A.B, A.C., B.D., C. F., A.I.R.H., A.J., D.K.J., G.J., R.N.K., M.L., A.L., B.L., J.L., M.M.T., H.M., M.M., P.M., E.N., S.O, L.O., A.R., S.S., R.T., F.V, O.W., S.Y, Y.Y, J.Z., H.Z.

Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.